

Research Contracts Benchmarking 2023

Public Report

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Executive Summary

Context

Research contract management is a critical function for all research-active universities as a foundation for constructive collaboration, achievement of strategic institutional research aims, and effective income growth. At the same time internal pressures driven by growth, complexity and a challenging climate for recruitment and retention impact on management, investment and skills. This report is intended to provide an evidence-based assessment of current practice, to assist those managing research contracts functions and inform future directions for policy.

Benchmarking research contracts

This report summarises the findings from a study examining and benchmarking research contract management at 24 universities in the UK (19) and Australia (5). The participating universities completed a common assessment framework in mid-2023. The participants represent a wide range of scales of activity: annual research incomes ranged from over £500m (A\$954m) to under £2m (A\$3.6m).

Collectively these 24 institutions reported on the activities of 240 research contract staff (in a range of leadership, managerial, officer and administrative roles, including temporary staff) who delivered a total of 22,465 new research contracts in 2022(-23). They completed more than 100,000 new agreements in the five years covered by the survey.

This project follows on from two previous research contracts benchmarking projects carried out by Research Consulting in 2013, on behalf of 20 UK research intensive institutions, and in 2018, for 19 UK and 11 Australian universities.

Areas of investigation

The study looked at key areas of research contract management, including research income, contract volumes, the staff and system resources in place, metrics and reporting and experience of external arbitration or litigation, as well as the costs, structures and remits of the research contracts functions in the participating universities.

Purpose of this report

This report is the final project output and is released as a public report to support further work and development in this area. The data related to individual universities is anonymised, but we draw out a number of comparisons and trends that may be helpful to those in strategic and operational leadership roles.

The number and range of participating institutions has allowed a number of comparisons to be drawn – by size (research income) and by territory (UK/Australia).

What the study shows – our overall findings

Research contract functions typically cost less than 1% of research income

For the participating universities, their research contract functions – including temporary staff and legal and other external advice costs – typically cost less than 1% of their institution's annual research income. But scale is a factor, and for institutions with lower research incomes the costs are proportionally higher.

Research contracts functions are mostly located within research office structures

The survey explored how research contracts functions are structured and governed. The majority of HEIs reported delivery through a central, dedicated research contracts team managed within the wider research office function. In the UK, only a small number (2 out of 19) form part of a central legal services team, whilst 2 out of 5 Australian participants

report at least partial responsibility for research contracts within the University's central legal services team. In the UK, there does seem to have been a shift since the previous survey – two of the research contracts teams which were based in legal services in 2018 are now based in the research office.

A range of staff roles are utilised in research contract functions

Research contracts functions deploy a range of staff roles to support research contracts, from administrative through to legally-qualified staff. As reported in 2018, contracts managers/officers are the backbone of the service for most universities, accounting for over half of reported full-time equivalent staff members (FTEs).

Recruitment and retention have become harder

In Australian and UK institutions, the general perception is that both recruitment and retention have become harder. The most frequently referenced method of addressing this has been through permitting hybrid working (nearly all participants), followed by around a third of participants reporting regrading roles, advertising contracts roles in new or different venues or increasing use of contractors.

Other / qualified by experience and professional legal qualifications are the two most frequently reported qualification types for contracts staff

19 of the 24 institutions reported having individuals with professional legal qualifications in the team. Aside from the largest institutions, this typically meant 1-3 individuals per contracts function.

Other / qualified by experience was the most reported qualification, both in terms of the number of institutions reporting this as present within their teams (nearly all participants) and in terms of the number of staff with this level of qualification.

Participants report growing complexity across a range of contract types

Participants report increased complexity across all types of agreements. In particular, data agreements, multilateral collaboration agreements, export licence applications and foreign influence / interference agreements (an agreement type specific to Australia only) are perceived to have increased significantly in complexity. Changes in legislation, particularly in UK data protection law, international collaborations and increased commercial considerations account for some of these changes in complexity since 2018.

A broad categorisation of contract types by complexity suggests that "more complex" contracts form the largest area of contract teams' work.

Availability and reporting of metrics for management purposes appears to have improved since 2018

Compared to the 2018 study, 2023 participants report much greater use of systems supporting contract management. Connected to this is a greater ability to report on a range of metrics associated with the management and workflow of contracts teams.

The study identifies 13 metrics relating to research contracts and 40% of the participants in 2023 could report against the majority of these. In 2018, 'total contract throughput' was the only measure reported by over half of the participants.

Electronic signature technology has been widely adopted...

A notable finding is the adoption of e-signature technology, which is used in 80% of participating institutions. We reported this as a notable opportunity for improvement in 2018, when none of the 30 participants reported using it. The enforced remote working during the COVID pandemic is widely recognised as the catalyst for change.

...but uptake of newer technologies remains limited

Around half of the participating institutions are at least aware of newer innovations, including AI review of third-party contracts, automated or AI-assisted drafting of new agreements and Word add-ins for contract drafting and review. However, operational use is currently very limited. Lack of budget, lack of contracts team capacity to investigate

potential solutions and lack of wider institutional capacity to implement software are seen as the most significant barriers to adoption of contracts management software.

International comparisons – similarities and differences

Approach to sign off authority Amongst both UK and Australian respondents, sign-off by a line manager (e.g. Director of Research Office, Director of Legal Services) or their delegate is the most frequently used sign-off route (used by just over half of the institutions in the study).

The average cost per contract is higher for Australian institutions In findings similar to those reported in 2018, on average, preparing a contract is more expensive in Australia than in the UK (£805 (A\$1,445) compared to £536 (A\$962) in the UK). The relative difference in salary costs between UK and Australian staff is a factor.

Salaries in Australia appear materially higher than for UK counterparts Australian starting salaries appear to be higher generally, especially for junior roles (such as contracts administrator and contracts assistant) and seem to have grown more since 2018. As in 2018, it appears that these salaries are higher in real terms, with part of the difference accounted for by the higher cost of living in Australia.¹

Australian institutions experienced a stronger growth in contract numbers Over recent years, the trend seen in 2018 of the volume of contracts increasing more significantly for Australian participants than for UK participants has continued, with Australian growth of 8% over the reporting period and UK growth of 6% over that time.

Differences in approach to governing law on international agreements We observed differences in the approach to governing law on international agreements. Australian participants prefer to remain silent on governing law when interacting with partners from other countries that do not accept Australian jurisdiction. This is not the case for UK participants, who are more likely to stipulate a mutually agreeable neutral jurisdiction.

Only a minority of respondents report any amount of arbitration / litigation in the last five years For the 2023 study we added a question on litigation or arbitration arising from research contracts to help understand how frequently this occurs. Participants reported a very small number of instances of contractual disputes being escalated to formal arbitration or litigation in the last five years. The reported instances are equivalent to less than 0.01% of the total contract volume in that period (UK) or 0.02% in Australia.

In the UK, Worktribe emerges as a leading provider of systems for managing research contracts Since 2018, adoption of Research Information Management Systems (RIMS), Current Research Information Systems (CRIS) and contract management software has increased, with two-thirds of institutions reporting implementation of these. Institutions with a lower research income (less than £10m (A\$18m)) are less likely to have any dedicated software. In the UK, Worktribe is reported as the most common provider of such software solutions. In the five Australian institutions the systems used are more varied.

The scale of research income makes a difference

Differences in organisational structures are aligned Dedicated research contracts teams located within the research office function are typical for universities with larger research incomes.

¹ Purchasing power parity suggests £0.68 equates to US\$1; whilst A\$1.42 equates to US\$1. OECD (2023). Purchasing power parities (PPP) (indicator). Doi: 10.1787/1290ee5a-en (Accessed on 1 November 2023).

to the overall scale of research income	<p>For those with smaller research incomes, the structures are more varied and may include formal responsibilities for legal services provision and multi-skilled central research office teams.</p> <p>The use of, and in some cases a reliance on, outsourced resource (e.g. temporary staff) is observed at all scales.</p>
Contracts functions in institutions with smaller research incomes are typically dealing with a wider range of agreement types, and hence additional complexity	<p>Typically, universities with the largest research incomes reported a narrower remit for their research contracts function. This is no doubt influenced by scale, with separate technology transfer offices, consultancy units/managers and clinical trial units able to deal with certain types of agreement.</p> <p>Contracts functions in institutions with smaller research incomes are typically dealing with a wider range of agreement types, and hence additional complexity.</p>
In Australia and the UK, overall contract volumes have fluctuated significantly	<p>In both Australia and the UK, overall contract volumes have fluctuated significantly over the reporting period, in part reflecting the effect of uncertainty associated with the COVID pandemic. In the UK, there have been notable increases in some types of contracts over this period, including data agreements, material transfer agreements, collaboration agreements and (unsurprisingly) total amendments, extensions and novations, which recorded their biggest increase (and the biggest increase of any agreement type, in any year) in 2019-20, as the COVID pandemic began.</p>
Workload measured by contracts per FTE is ~100 on average, but varies considerably	<p>Workload, measured through a “contracts per FTE” indicator, was highly variable between institutions, ranging from 40 to over 180. This measure was not particularly influenced by scale (research income). The average was ~100 contracts per FTE, and the majority of institutions reported workloads in a range between 80 and 120 contracts per FTE.</p>

Conclusion

Conclusion	<p>Whilst many of the issues and characteristics of contracts management identified in 2018 remain the same, there have been particular areas of notable change, such as widespread adoption of e-signature technology and improved use of metrics and systems.</p> <p>This report identifies a number of areas for future consideration, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• addressing a challenging recruitment and retention landscape;• building on opportunities to enhance training (including on a regional or partnership basis);• sharing of insight and experience of adoption of dedicated software for research contract management, informing procurement decisions and optimising use of data;• scoping and awareness-raising regarding the use and adoption of technologies (including AI) which can assist in contracts work; and• working across the sector to consider areas where further standardisation may be helpful.
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1. Background and approach

1.1 Introduction

About this report

Research contract management is a critical function for all research-active universities. The professional staff employed in delivering research contracts are highly skilled but are dealing with ever-increasing complexity and volumes in their day-to-day roles.

External partners and businesses are seeking greater value from their university relationships. Governments and funding bodies are also placing increased expectations on institutions to deliver economic and social impact. At the same time, internal pressures driven by growth, increased complexity and a challenging context for recruitment and retention impact on management, investment and skills.

This report summarises the findings from a study examining and benchmarking research contract management at 24 universities in the UK and Australia. It is intended to provide an evidence-based assessment of current practice, to assist those managing research contracts functions and inform policymakers.

1.2 Background

Why a 2023 research contracts benchmarking exercise?

This report builds on two previous exercises, in 2013 (UK only) and in 2018 (UK and Australia). This series of reports documents the evolving landscape of research contract management practices and trends.

The **2013 benchmarking exercise** compared the research contracts functions of institutions in the Brunswick Group of UK research intensive universities. This was commissioned in response to the perceived growth in complexity and volume of research contracts managed by universities and the critical role they play in supporting effective relationships between universities and business.

Research Consulting then revisited the topic of research contracts in our 2016 **report** for HEFCE on Effective Practice in Knowledge Exchange. This demonstrated the availability of a number of reference materials to help institutions manage their contracts, particularly from ARMA and PraxisAuril.

In 2018, a further **research contracts benchmarking exercise** involved a broader range of universities and introduced an international dimension to the benchmarks, comparing 19 UK and 11 Australian universities.

The 2013, 2018 and 2023 data collection methodology is consistent, but for the 2023 survey, we have added new areas to the survey, including:

- recruitment and retention;
- use of AI and other systems; and
- experience of external arbitration and litigation.

Although the participants in the 2013, 2018 and 2023 surveys have varied, 14 of the 19 UK participants in 2023 have been involved in at least one of the previous two surveys, enabling some comparisons to be made over 10 years.

Our detailed findings have already been shared with the project participants, and this public report shares the high-level findings with the wider community.

Figure 1 shows the overlap between UK participants in 2023 and in the two earlier surveys.

Figure 1
Participation in previous
Research Contracts
Benchmarking projects

About the participants

The 19 UK and five Australian participants reflect the diversity of the landscape of universities in the UK and Australia, including level of research income and intensity, disciplinary mix and geographic spread. Research incomes for the participating universities ranged from £2m (A\$3.6m) to over £531m (A\$954m), and research contracts teams ranged from less than 1 full-time equivalent member of staff (FTE) to just over 30 FTEs.

The participants' research contracts functions involve 240 contracts staff, in a range of leadership, officer, administrative and temporary roles, who delivered a total of 22,465 new research contracts in 2022(-23). Collectively, the institutions saw the completion of more than 100,000 new agreements in the five years covered by the survey (at least 93,549 in the UK and 10,523 in Australia, with some under-reporting noted in earlier years).

Within this report we have anonymised the data relating to *individual* universities, but are able to confirm the names of participating universities:

United Kingdom

Cranfield University
Durham University
Edge Hill University
Loughborough University
Queen's University Belfast
SOAS

Bangor University
University College London
University of Edinburgh
University of Hull
University of Leicester
University of Manchester
University of Northumbria at Newcastle

University of Nottingham
University of Reading
University of Sheffield
University of Southampton
University of Surrey
University of Westminster

Australia

Charles Sturt University
Flinders University
RMIT University
University of Adelaide
University of Canberra

The 2023 benchmarking project

Participation in the project entailed the following:

- a specialist benchmarking exercise consisting of an online questionnaire which addressed team structure, size, skills, remit, contract volume and workload, legal and governance considerations, and use of systems and metrics for reporting;
- a bespoke institutional performance report and supporting analysis;
- a 1-to-1 consultation with our team to discuss the institutional context and performance; and
- attendance at an in-person good practice sharing event (UK participants only) and a virtual workshop (for Australian participants).

This report is our final project output and includes anonymised results drawn from our analysis of all data gathered in the course of this project.

Timeline

Invitations to participate were issued from February 2023 and the data collection phase with confirmed participants commenced in May 2023. Bespoke institutional reports and supporting analysis were delivered in September 2023, followed by institution-specific feedback meetings and an in-person good practice workshop for UK participants and a virtual workshop for Australian participants.

A draft version of this report was shared with project participants in January 2024.

Our team

To ensure a good coverage of all topics and issues relevant to the international research contracts landscape, we built a multi-disciplinary team. This included:

- Research Consulting
 - Rob Johnson – Managing Director and project lead
 - Dr Dan King – Director
 - Dr Angharad Roberts – Senior Analyst and project manager
 - Frances Palmer – Associate Consultant and data analyst
- Associate Consultants
 - Tom Morgan – Legal expert
 - Dr Mark Hochman – Australasia expert

Further information on the consulting team is in [Appendix A](#).

1.3 Terms of reference

Objectives of project

The overall objective of the study was to benchmark university research contracts functions and facilitate the sharing of good practice. The detailed objectives were to:

- Benchmark resourcing levels for the contracts functions at participating institutions, using relevant measures such as staff costs, salary grades and FTEs, and the proportion of professionally qualified versus qualified by experience contracts staff.
- Benchmark overall volume levels relating to contract activity and its complexity against the level of FTE resource deployed (e.g. volume and type of different contract types), allowing for size and shape of the organisation and organisational structure where possible.
- Ascertain the workflows typically used to manage research contracts, including delegated authority, sign-off arrangements and use of systems including those utilising Artificial Intelligence.
- Identify variations in the roles and responsibilities of contracts management staff, consider how these fit into overall research and knowledge exchange functions, and assess any implications for process efficiency and service quality.
- Highlight areas of change or challenge in relation to recruitment and retention.
- Highlight areas of good practice and document case studies that can be drawn on by institutions seeking to improve the performance of their contracts functions.
- Review the interface between research, consultancy and legal/commercial service contracting to understand overall workload of the contracts function.
- Facilitate networking and exchange of information between participating institutions.

1.4 Methodology

Area of investigation

The study looked at key areas of research contract management, including research income, contract volumes, the staff and system resources in place, metrics and reporting and experience of external arbitration or litigation, as well as the costs, structures and remits of the research contracts functions in the participating universities.

Development of a specialist survey

Working with our associates and participating universities, Research Consulting developed a comprehensive online survey. This built upon and improved our 2013 and 2018 approach and addressed issues currently of concern to research contracts managers.

The majority of questions were common to UK and Australian participants. However, some questions were specific to location, such as those around the use of sector template agreements (e.g. the Lambert agreements in the UK, or the ARC Multi-institutional agreement in Australia).

To support consistency in understanding and data capture, we held four webinars for project participants, addressing how survey questions should be interpreted.

We collected data on several quantitative and qualitative aspects of research contracts management, and the survey captured information on the following areas:

- **Institutional details:** research income and funding mix.

- **The research contracts function:** structure, governance, FTEs and delivery.
- **Staffing levels and costs:** roles, skills/qualification, training, costs of temporary or outsourced resource, recruitment and retention.
- **The role of the research contracts function:** remit, services and activities / responsibilities undertaken.
- **Contract activity levels:** volume of research contracts by type and split by discipline.
- **Contract complexity and risk:** sign-off of agreements, contract complexity, volume and risk management, treatment of contracts in other jurisdictions.
- **Template agreements:** the extent and nature of use.
- **Management systems and reporting:** use of metrics and reporting, adoption of software solutions (including use of AI).
- **Contractual disputes:** Numbers and types of contracts subject to external arbitration or litigation.

The participants completed the survey during June and July 2023.

The data looked at the five financial years covering 2018/19 to 2022/23. It should be noted that a small offset exists between the timing of these in the UK and Australia:

- For the UK participants this meant the five financial years starting in August 2018 and ending in July 2023.
- For the Australian participants this refers to the five calendar years starting in January 2018 and ending in December 2022.

Where possible, data for the UK 2018/19 financial year are presented alongside the Australian data for the 2018 calendar year & shown as '2018(/19)'; data for the UK 2022/23 financial year (forecast research income) are presented alongside the Australian data for the 2022 calendar year and shown as '2022(/23)'.

Reporting

We prepared bespoke institutional reports for all project participants, including comparisons with their peers and insights arising from the calls held with their representatives.

This public report provides a summary of the main project findings, including insights from both Australian and UK institutions.

In addition, all monetary figures in this report are given both in GBP (£) and AUD (A\$). The exchange rate used is **£1 GBP to A\$1.8** and is based on the average (mean) of quarterly exchange rates during the period January 2022 to June 2023, as reported by the UK [Office of National Statistics](#).

Anonymisation of the project data

For the purposes of public dissemination, this report does not identify data associated with individual participating institutions.

To assist readers in interpreting the study findings, we have defined three institutional 'groups' based on the scale of research income (in 2022/23 for UK and 2022 for Australian participants). This uses the same scale boundaries as per the 2018 public report and analysis to support comparisons. For 2023:

- Group A comprises seven universities, with research incomes >£100m / >A\$180m; the average for this group is £245m / A\$440m.
- Group B comprises 10 institutions with research incomes between £20m and £100m / between A\$36m and \$180m; the average is £54m / A\$97m.

- Group C comprises seven universities with research incomes below £20m / A\$36m; the average is £10m / A\$18m.

These groups are intended to allow readers to more effectively interpret the report's conclusions and analysis and apply them to their own institutional contexts. Certain charts and figures identify the individual institutions by Group A/B/C and/or location.

Where barcharts are used which list the Groups of individual participating institutions, the charts are organised in descending order based on responses to each specific question, with the highest response to the question placed first. The "first" institution listed will not necessarily represent the same project participant throughout this report (i.e. the report is fully anonymised as opposed to being simply pseudonymised).

Limitations and exclusions While the project sought to obtain a balanced picture of institutions' approaches to the management of research contracts, the following limitations on the scope of work should be noted:

- The accuracy of the data submitted as part of the survey phase of the project remains the responsibility of the participating institutions. The project team worked with participating institutions to review and revise their data submissions to the extent reasonably possible. We have however not sought to audit these submissions and cannot accept responsibility for any errors in interpretation resulting from the submitted information.
- This exercise did not aim to investigate the *quality* of the service provided by the contracts functions under consideration. Therefore, analysis and conclusions around productivity cannot be used to assess the quality of the service provided to internal stakeholders (typically academic staff) or to third parties (such as industrial sponsors of research). An exercise to fully examine quality would need a different approach.
- Our analysis is based on the observations and comments from a self-selected group of project participants. Whilst the participating universities appear to be sufficiently varied to reflect aspects of the wider sector in a useful and broadly representative way, care should be taken in interpretation or extrapolation of the findings contained within this report. The purpose of the exercise was primarily to inform the participating universities and not to establish representative sector-wide benchmarks.

Acknowledgements The support and assistance of contracts and research office staff at the participating institutions has been invaluable in the preparation of this report. An additional thank you is extended to those universities and individuals who have supplied case studies for this report.

2. Findings of the exercise

2.1 The institutional context

This report reflects survey responses from a wide range of institutions

Participating institutions ranged from small and specialist institutions to large, research-intensive universities. The participants' research incomes in 2022(/23) ranged from around £2m (A\$3.6m) to over £530m (A\$954m) (Figure 2). The research incomes of the five Australian institutions means that at least one is represented in each research income group (A, B or C).

Compared to the 2018 participants, the distribution of institutional research incomes is similar overall. However, we note that the research income for the largest participating institution in 2023 is twice that in 2018. This range of participating institutions provides a representative, but not comprehensive, view on research contract management in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in the UK and Australia. The work of the UK participants supported forecast research income of over £2bn (A\$3.6bn) in 2022-23; in Australia, contracts team activities supported research income of £278m (A\$499m) in 2022.

Figure 2

Profile of research incomes for the 24 participating institutions

Based on reported 2022/23 (UK) and 2022 (Aus) income data

The chart also indicates the income Group A, B or C

The majority of participants report dedicated research contracts functions within the research office

The survey explored how research contracts functions are structured and governed (Table 1). The majority of HEIs reported delivery through a central, dedicated research contracts team managed within the wider research office function. 13 of the 24 participants reported this approach as delivering the entirety of their research contracts function. A further five institutions report delivery structures based on this *in combination* with other structures or approaches, including:

- the university's legal services function;
- faculty or college-based devolved contracts functions; and

- other multi-skilled teams within the wider Research Office.

Contracts provision is also delivered through legal services, faculty-based teams and outsourced providers

Only two institutions (one UK, one Australian) reported research contracts work being delivered solely through the university legal services function. Larger institutions are more likely to deploy a combination of structures, including devolved faculty/college contracts teams (although all feature a central research-office based contracts function). For the group with lower research income, the structures are more varied and may include outsourced provision, alignment with wider legal services provision or a multi-skilled central research office team.

In the UK, there does seem to have been a shift since the previous survey – two of the research contracts teams which were based in legal services in 2018 are now based in the research office.

Table 1 Type of organisational structure used, including delivery wholly or in part by using each structure

	Central, dedicated research contracts team within research office	Central, multi-skilled team within research office	Faculty/ College-based contracts teams	Central, dedicated team, with some specialist roles located elsewhere	Research contracts managed by University legal services function	Research contracts outsourced to external provider	No of unique HEIs involved
Delivered entirely via this structure	13	2	0	0	2	0	17
Reported partially being delivered using this structure (in combination)	5	4	3	1	3	2	7

Interfaces with pre-award, post-award and business development teams are high frequency and important

The exercise examined the frequency and importance of interactions with other departments and professional services (see Figure 3). ‘High frequency and high importance’ interactions are identified with five other functional areas:

- pre-award;
- post award;
- information compliance;
- consultancy offices/services; and
- research business development / partnerships functions.

With the exception of information compliance, these teams are often, but not always, incorporated within the same departmental structure.

Less frequent, but important, interactions are identified with:

- legal services;
- clinical governance;
- commercialisation (technology transfer); and
- insurance.

In the UK the European Funding Team is also identified as high importance.

Figure 3 The frequency and importance of internal interactions by research contracts functions

CASE STUDY: Creating a contracting hub

Durham University (UK)

At Durham, research contracts were managed by Legal Services who were responsible for reviewing, drafting and arranging signature for all contracts and funder award letters. The pre award team in Research and Innovation Services (RIS) were responsible for requesting the work and acted as a go between for internal and external parties, completing negotiations and handling queries, often without relevant tools or appropriate knowledge, alongside other competing priorities. Recognising the sector has seen a rapid and sustained growth in the volume and complexity of research and research-related contracts, it was essential we looked to develop and implement research contracting approaches that were more efficient and responsive, whilst identifying and proportionately managing the range of risks inherent in delivering research in an increasingly challenging environment.

We recognised that our research contracting processes were slower than in other research-intensive universities leading to dissatisfaction from academic staff and external partners, and a new streamlined approach with clearly defined ownership and accountability was needed.

A programme of change was developed to move the ownership of research contracting into RIS.

The first stage was to embed a new contracting hub within the Research Operations Team with a focus on designing a suite of standard templates, developing a risk and escalation framework, and implementing the Worktribe Contracts Module. The new hub still worked very closely with Legal Services, who were still heavily involved in the review of contracts. This created duplication of effort between the teams and lack of clarity on roles and responsibilities.

The second stage therefore focussed on the transfer of end-to-end ownership of the contracting process into RIS, with Legal Services responsible for managing the arrangement of signatures. This was completed in March 2023, and with investment into the team the contracting hub grew from 2 FTE to 4 FTE.

We now have a process improvement programme underway, including the move to Adobe Sign and establishing an academic advisory group to help inform and shape our service provision, and we are increasing communications to raise the profile of the team and our visibility. We will be using the outcomes from the benchmarking exercise and workshop to put in place better ways of working to reduce our contract turn round times, measure our performance, and improve our service delivery.

2.2 Scope of the contracts function

Introduction

The survey asked about the remit of the contracts function in terms of types of agreements handled and other activities undertaken. Generally, contracts functions in institutions with lower levels of research income reported a broader remit than larger institutions.

The scope of contracts functions, considering agreement types and other activities, and range of research income

The survey sought to understand the breadth and scope of the remit of the research contracts function. This looked at **agreement types** (Figure 4) and selected **other activities** (Figure 5), for example due diligence on new funders or sponsors. The methodology assumes that all contracts functions have responsibility for industrial research contracts, research subcontracts, studentships, non-disclosure agreements (NDAs) and collaboration agreements.

Typically, universities with the largest research incomes reported a narrower remit for their research contracts function, reflecting the fact these institutions may have separate technology transfer offices, consultancy units/managers and clinical trial units focusing on dealing with specific types of agreement. Contracts functions in institutions with smaller research incomes are typically dealing with a wider range of agreement types, and therefore additional complexity.

Teams typically have primary responsibility for material transfer agreements, data agreements, and consultancy agreements

The types of agreement which both UK and Australian respondents most frequently have primary responsibility for are Material Transfer Agreements, data agreements and consultancy agreements.

UK institutions also frequently have primary responsibility for European Commission agreements and knowledge transfer agreements (e.g. KTP agreements). The Australian participants appear to have primary responsibility for a slightly smaller number of agreement types. In addition to the most frequent agreement types noted above for both UK and Australian institutions, over half of the Australian universities have primary responsibility for services rendered (both by and to the university), international research project agreements (used as an Australia-specific category of agreement, broadly comparable to EC agreements in the UK) and agreements with indigenous peoples.

Contracts functions typically have shared responsibility for activities

Contracts functions typically have primary, or more frequently, shared responsibility for a number of **other activities** relating to funder terms and conditions, due diligence, compliance and assurance. Monitoring changes in public research funders' terms and

relating to due diligence, compliance and assurance. conditions is the most commonly held responsibility for contracts functions. Virtually all institutions report this as a primary or shared responsibility for contracts functions.

Two further activities are held as responsibilities by around two-thirds of the participants: (i) due diligence on new funders, customers and partners and (ii) checking and assurance review of costing and pricing for contracts.

Around half of participants report primary or (more typically) shared responsibility for checking and assurance reviews of five compliance-related issues:

- compliance with UK export controls;
- compliance with the UK National Security and Investment act;
- information compliance;
- compliance with the Nagoya Protocol; and
- compliance with cyber security arrangements.

Figure 4 Agreement types for which contract teams have primary (P), shared (S), ad hoc (A) or no responsibility (N) (types used in both UK and Australia)

	Contracts team remit	Material Transfer agreements	Data agreements	Sponsorship agreements	Consultancy agreements	Services rendered agreements (BY the university)	Agreements (software or non-software)	Services rendered agreements (TO the university)	Export licence applications	Spinout company agreements	Capital and equipment agreements	Agreements relating to philanthropic donations	Staff secondment agreements
Institution Group		Commonly within remit											Farely
		within remit											
Group C	Broad 	P	P	P	P	P	P	P	P	P	P	P	P
Group C		P	P	P	P	P	P	P	P	N	S	S	P
Group B		P	P	P	P	P	P	P	S	P	P	N	N
Group C		P	P	P	P	S	P	S	P	P	P	S	S
Group B		P	P	A	P	P	P	A	P	P	A	P	A
Group B		P	P	P	P	N	P	N	P	P	A	N	N
Group C		P	P	P	P	P	P	P	P	A	S	P	N
Group B		P	S	P	P	P	P	S	S	A	A	A	A
Group C		P	P	A	P	P	P	P	A	N	N	N	A
Group B		P	P	P	S	P	S	P	S	S	P	P	S
Group A		P	P	A	P	P	S	P	N	N	S	N	S
Group B		P	P	N	N	P	N	N	N	N	A	N	P
Group A		P	P	P	A	S	S	S	P	N	S	A	A
Group B		P	P	P	S	A	A	P	A	N	S	N	N
Group A		P	P	S	P	S	S	N	A	A	A	N	S
Group A		P	P	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	S	A	A
Group A		P	P	S	P	S	S	A	N	N	A	N	S
Group B		P	S	P	A	P	A	A	N	N	A	N	A
Group B		P	S	P	N	S	S	S	N	N	S	S	S
Group C		S	S	S	P	P	S	P	S	S	N	A	N
Group B	P	S	N	S	S	N	S	N	N	S	N	N	
Group A	P	P	S	S	A	A	A	A	N	A	N	N	
Group C	N	N	N	S	S	S	N	S	N	N	N	N	
Group A	Narrow	S	S	A	N	N	S	A	N	N	S	N	

Figure 5 Activity types for which contract teams have primary (P), shared (S), ad hoc (A) or no responsibility (N) (activities applicable in both UK and Australia)

	Contracts team remit	Monitoring changes in public research funders' terms and conditions	Due diligence on new funders, customers and partners	Checking and assurance review of costing and pricing for contracts	Checking and assurance review of information compliance	Checking and assurance review on compliance with the Nagoya Protocol	Checking and assurance review on compliance with cyber security arrangements	Checking and assurance review for the University on matters of employment law	Checking and assurance review for the University on matters of property law
Institution Group		Commonly within remit						Farely within remit	
		within remit							
Group C	Broad 	P	P	A	S	P	S	N	N
Group C		P	P	P	P	S	S	A	N
Group B		P	P	P	S	S	S	N	N
Group B		S	S	S	S	S	P	N	N
Group B		P	N	S	S	P	S	N	N
Group A		P	S	N	S	S	S	N	N
Group C		S	A	N	P	N	A	P	P
Group A		S	P	P	A	N	A	N	N
Group B		S	P	A	A	S	A	A	A
Group B		P	S	P	N	N	A	N	N
Group A		P	S	A	A	S	S	A	A
Group A		P	A	A	S	S	S	N	N
Group B		P	S	A	A	A	A	N	N
Group B		S	S	S	A	N	S	N	N
Group B		S	A	S	P	S	S	N	N
Group A		P	A	N	S	N	A	N	N
Group C		P	S	S	S	N	A	N	N
Group C		S	P	S	N	N	N	N	N
Group C		P	S	N	N	N	N	N	N
Group A		S	S	S	S	S	S	N	N
Group C	S	N	S	A	A	A	N	N	
Group B	S	N	N	N	A	N	N	N	
Group B	S	A	A	A	N	A	N	N	
Group A	Narrow	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	

2.3 Staffing levels and costs

Introduction

The methodology gathered data on staffing levels, roles, and costs for each research contracts function. Similar to the 2018 project findings, larger institutions have a notably lower cost of the contracts function as a proportion of research income compared to smaller ones. Australian institutions generally have higher salary ranges than their UK counterparts. Recruitment and retention challenges have increased in the past five years, prompting contracts functions to adopt hybrid working to address these issues.

The cost of research contracts functions as a percentage of overall research income

As in 2018, data on the costs of research contracts functions (staff and other reported costs, temporary staff and additional legal advice) as a percentage of overall research income clearly identifies the benefits of scale (see Table 2). The profile for 2023 participants in Figure 6 illustrates the influence of research income on relative costs. In interpreting this analysis, it should be borne in mind that larger universities are more likely to demonstrate features that would contribute to this outcome, including:

- the magnitude of difference between the research incomes in Group A and Group C is considerable: research incomes at institutions in Group A range from six to 246 times greater than incomes at institutions in Group C;
- the narrower remit of the research contracts functions in Group A universities;
- economies of scale that can be achieved as research contracts team grow, for example the use of junior and administrative staff; and
- a greater occurrence of major research projects (£1m+, A\$1.8m+) which increase research income more significantly than contract volume.

Table 2

2018 and 2023 comparisons of cost of the contracts function as a % of research income

	2018(/19)	2022(/23)
Group A (>£100m, A\$180m)	0.4% (n=6)	0.39% (n=7)
Group B (£20m to £100m)	0.7% (n=13)	0.99% (n=10)
Group C (under £20m, A\$36m)	1.3% (n=11)	1.7% (n=7)
Total	0.9% (n=30)	0.57% (n=24)

Figure 6

Percentage of research income 2022(/23) spent on contracts function costs (including permanent and temporary staff and legal and other external advice costs) (one outlying institution is not shown)

Of the staff delivering research contracts, over half of the reported roles were Contracts Officers or Contracts Managers.

The exercise examined the roles and seniority of FTEs that comprised the research contracts functions reported within the study. These were reported against six 'generic' roles to allow comparison across institutions:

- Head of Section;
- Senior Contracts Manager;
- Contracts Manager;
- Contracts Officer;
- Contracts Assistant; and
- Contracts Administrator.

In total 240 FTEs were reported by the 24 institutions, including temporary staff, ranging from 33 FTE for the largest function, down to 0.8 FTE in the smallest (Figure 7). Leadership is provided at varying levels of seniority – 16 teams are led by heads of section, 5 are led by senior contracts managers and 2 by contracts managers. As was the case in 2018, the most frequently occurring job roles were Contracts Officers and Contracts Managers, with over half of FTEs reported to be in these roles.

Figure 7
The staffing composition of research contracts functions

Australian starting salaries appear to be higher generally, especially for junior roles and seem to have grown more since 2018

Respondents were asked to report the minimum, maximum and super maximum salary for salary scales of their current staff as they corresponded to the specific role titles at different seniority levels. These were salary ranges excluding on-costs.

Compared to 2018, salaries have increased slightly in the UK. For example, for contracts officers, the normal salary range has increased from £31k-£38k (A\$56k-A\$68k) in 2018 to £33k-£44k (A\$59k-A\$79k) (2023) and for contracts managers this has increased from £39k-£47k (A\$70k-A\$84k) in 2018 to £41k-£54k (A\$74k-A\$97k) in 2023. These are below inflation increases.

Australian salary range minimums are generally significantly higher than for UK participants, especially in junior roles such as contracts administrator or contracts assistant roles, with salaries starting above £40k (A\$71k). Contracts officer roles start at £55k (A\$99k), which is higher than the £43k (A\$77k) salary minimum in 2018, suggesting higher levels of salary growth over that time (although noting the different participating institutions in 2023). As in 2018, it appears that these salaries are higher in real terms, with only part of the difference accounted for by the higher cost of living in Australia.

Additional costs are commonly incurred through a need for temporary staff or additional legal advice

Vacancies and peaks in workload or backlogs are managed through temporary or agency staff, with 16 universities reporting the use of temporary staff in 2022(/23) with an average spend of £84k (A\$151k) amongst the institutions which used these.

Of the 16 institutions using temporary staff, eight also used external legal or other specialist advice, and one other institution used external advice but not temporary staff. Figure 8 indicates the spend on these additional costs and resources to support contracts activities across institutions in 2022(/23). For these nine participants reporting expenditure on additional legal costs, the average cost was £16k (A\$29k).

Figure 8
Spend on temporary staff and external legal and other specialist advice

CASE STUDY:
Overcoming contract backlogs

Flinders University
(Australia)

Flinders University found themselves in a position where the backlog of contracts requiring assessment was compromising their ability to provide service to researchers at the level required. Their budget for recruitment was insufficient to employ new ongoing staff, or to afford externally contracted legal firms to reduce the backlog. Instead they looked within the university, employing final year law students to work, under supervision, on the more standard contract types. This had the double effect of

providing practical work experience for students whilst also assisting the Research Office reduce the backlog to more manageable levels.

Was this a long term solution? Whilst some students were subsequently employed by the Research Office the university found that the rapid exposure to contract assessments assisted students to develop the experience that made them highly desirable to external organisations with the university unable to match salaries or career opportunities being provided by private firms. The Research Office concluded that whilst this was an effective practice in reducing immediate contract overloads that it was not a sustainable, long-term solution.

Cost of contracts function per FTE

The survey asked participants to report total spend on staff, including on-costs.

The average (mean) cost of the contracts function per FTE – calculated as the sum of staffing costs (permanent and temporary staff) plus legal and other external advice costs, divided by the total number of FTE (including temporary staff) – across all UK respondents is £53k (A\$95k). For Australian participants, this is £73k (A\$131k). (Without temporary staff or legal and other advice costs, this falls to £50k (A\$90k) in the UK and £66k (A\$118k) in Australia.)

There is also some apparent correlation between the size of the staff team and the research income of the institution (Figure 9).

Figure 9
Correlation of research income to staff FTEs for (2022/23)

Other / qualified by experience and professional legal qualifications are the two most frequently reported qualification types for contracts staff

Against each contracts team member reported, the participating institutions indicated their highest qualification, across four qualification categories:

- Professional legal qualifications;
- Postgraduate research degree;
- Law degree; or
- Other / qualified by experience.

19 of the 24 institutions reported having individuals with professional legal qualifications in the team. Aside from the largest institutions, this typically meant 1-3 individuals per contracts function.

Other / qualified by experience was the most reported qualification, both in terms of the number of institutions reporting this as present within their teams (20) and in terms of the number of staff with this level of qualification (116).

There is a slightly different pattern of qualifications between the UK and Australia, with the largest proportion of UK FTE reported as "Other / qualified by experience" compared to Australia, where a slightly larger proportion have a Law degree.

In most institutions, both recruitment and retention are perceived to have become more difficult over the past five years

Institutions were asked to reflect on changes in recruitment and retention over the last five years, in terms of difficulty (Figure 10), and to indicate methods they have used to manage this. Institutions were additionally asked to indicate the training options and providers available to their contracts staff.

Most institutions responding to the survey have found both recruitment and retention becoming harder. The most frequently referenced method of addressing this has been through permitting hybrid working (23 participants), followed by regrading roles (9), advertising contracts roles in new or different venues (8) and increasing use of contractors (8).

The most frequent form of training provided is internal training by the local team, followed by internal training by institutional professional development teams and PraxisAuril and ARMA courses in the UK or by ARMS or KCA in Australia. Institutions with higher research income seem to be more likely to offer courses by external legal advisers (paid-for or pro bono).

Figure 10 Perceptions of changing situation in relation to recruitment and retention (count of HEIs by group in each category)

CASE STUDY:
Nottingham’s experience of training and development
 University of Nottingham (UK)

Driven by sector-wide issues, including challenges in recruitment and retention, relatively high use of fixed-term contracts and locums to cover vacancies and peaks in demand, and COVID-related increases in contract workload, Nottingham initiated a **lean review** to identify areas for improvement. This led to a programme of investment in resource, focussing on growing local talent and forward-planning.

A business case was submitted to invest in resource and bring staffing levels back to pre-pandemic levels. Retention was supported through moving staff to permanent contracts, provision of additional administrative support, increasing CPD and training opportunities (including internal training co-ordinated with Legal Services) and actively encouraging staff progression through promotion. The average case load per FTE has been significantly reduced and is monitored on an ongoing basis. Contractors are used to cover gaps during recruitment and opportunities are open to non-lawyer professionals with the right ability and experience.

The situation is monitored on an on-going basis and further work is planned with HR regarding well-being and staff sickness. A team building event has focused on living values. There are also plans to implement annual recruitment of a level 3 intern on a training route, offering a pipeline for resource and potentially reducing / removing the reliance on contractors. The Research Division has also begun hosting work shadowing at Research Contracts Assistant level.

2.4 Contract volume and workload

Introduction

Trends in contract volume has been highly variable over the last five years, although overall there has been growth in both the UK and Australia. Some contract types have shown particularly strong growth including amendments, extensions and novations (peaking in the pandemic period) and, in the UK, data agreements,

The advantages of scale are seen in the cost and time taken per contract, as well as in the cost of contracts function per FTE.

Trends in contracts volume The number of new contracts each year for the five years (2018(/19) to 2022(/23)) covered by the survey was assessed. This considered annual volumes and types of agreement. The impact of COVID from early 2020 should be recognised.

The pattern in contract volume over the last five years has been highly variable, although there is an overall pattern of growth of 6% in the total number of new contracts amongst the 13 UK institutions which have submitted complete data for all five years. The three Australian institutions reporting complete data for five years showed a more robust increase of 8.3% over that time.

In the UK, there have been notable increases in some types of contracts over this period, including data agreements (up over 70%), material transfer agreements, collaboration agreements and total amendments, extensions and novations (up over 60%). The latter recorded their biggest increase (and the biggest increase of any agreement type, in any year) in 2019-20, as the COVID pandemic began. Trends by agreement type are less clear in Australia, where the total number of contracts is much smaller and complete data for all five years is only available for some of the five institutions.

Similar to the 2018 project, non-income bearing agreements (CDAs, MTAs, MoUs) make up 23% of overall contract volume.

Different patterns of change in volume are apparent in the five contract types which account for the largest total activity (9,000-15,500 agreements in total between 2018-2023, based on data from 16 institutions reporting complete data for all five years (n=16)). This includes amendments, extensions and novations, where increased volume is particularly apparent in the pandemic period 2020(/21) (Figure 11).

Figure 11

Pattern of change in volume for contract types accounting for the largest total activity

Data agreements have shown a particularly large increase; studentship agreements and European Commission agreements have reduced

There are similarly varied and distinctive patterns of change amongst the group of contract types which account for the second largest set of activity (600–4,500 agreements in total). This includes a large increase in numbers of data agreements, particularly in the UK and particularly in institutions with larger research income. In the UK, the reporting period covers the whole timeframe since the Data Protection Act (2018) became law.

Studentship agreements and European Commission agreements have shown particularly notable declines over the course of the five-year reporting period (Figure 12).

Figure 12

Pattern of change in volume accounting for second largest group of contract types

Workload of contracts staff Across the 19 UK participants there is an average of 98.5 new contracts per FTE (104.7 contracts per FTE excluding temporary staff, and 114.8 contracts per FTE excluding both temporary staff and administrators). For the Australian institutions reporting FTE numbers there is an average of 90.8 contracts per FTE (94.0 contracts per FTE excluding temporary staff and 112.9 per FTE excluding temporary staff and administrators) (Figure 13).

Four smaller universities with research incomes below £20m (A\$36m) reported volumes of more than 110 contracts per FTE, higher than the number of contracts per FTE of 11 larger universities.

Figure 13

Number of new contracts in 2022(/23) per FTE (including temporary staff)

Factors in allocating work The survey examined the factors that affect the allocation of workload within contracts teams. Over half of responding institutions indicate that type of contract or existing workload distribution are either ranked first or second as key factors affecting allocation of workload (Figure 14).

Figure 14
Priorities for allocation of workload within contracts functions

Cost and time to process agreements Reported costs for the contracts function (permanent staff salaries, on-costs, temporary staff, and external advice costs) divided by the number of new contracts in 2022(/23) yielded an average cost per contract. Similarly, multiplying the reported full-time equivalents (FTE) within the contracts function by 1,650 (approximate working hours per year) and dividing by the number of new contracts provided an approximate time to process per contract. Both calculations can also be refined by excluding FTE associated with temporary contract function support or external advice costs.

Based on these calculations, the average cost per contract for UK participants is £536 (A\$962) (including temporary staff and legal costs) or £480 (A\$862) (excluding temporary staff and legal costs). The average time to process agreements is 16.8 hours (including temporary staff) or 15.8 hours (excluding temporary staff). For Australian participants, the average cost per contract is £805 (A\$1,445) (including temporary staff) or £704 (A\$1,264) (excluding temporary staff). The average time to process agreements is 18.2 hours (including temporary staff) or 17.5 hours (excluding temporary staff).

Both cost and time per contract decrease significantly for institutions with larger research incomes. Across UK and Australian institutions, Group A institutions have a mean cost per contract 41% lower than Group C, and a mean time to process each contract 20% lower than Group C. The distribution of institutions by cost and time per contract is illustrated in Figure 15.

Figure 15
Hours per contract vs cost per contract

CASE STUDY: Sheffield's experience of managing large volumes of contracts
University of Sheffield (UK)

As one of the busiest contracts teams involved in this project, receiving on average 3,000 contract requests per year, Sheffield's Contracts Team seeks to optimise efficient handling of agreements through effective team organisation; appropriate allocation of work; consistent contract processes; and managing workload at individual level.

Sheffield has staff in roles at six levels: Contracts Support Team (Administrator / Apprentice); Assistant Contracts Officer, Contracts Officer, Contracts Manager, Senior Contracts Manager, Contracts Team Manager.

Contracts are allocated based on contract type and complexity, understood at five "core" levels, from standard agreements ("Core 0") handled by the Contracts Support Team, to "Core 4" – complex or non-standard industry and government funded agreements – which are the responsibility of Senior Contract Managers.

The contracts process begins with the submission of an electronic agreement request form. The Contracts Support Team set up new records and add them to the pipeline. On Friday afternoon each week, unallocated agreements are reported and prioritised, and are then allocated within the team at a weekly Monday meeting for first review.

The amount of new contracts allocated to individual team members each week varies depending on their current active workload and other considerations such as upcoming annual leave. There is an aim to achieve a balance between workload and team

development, supporting a learning culture within the team and providing stretch activities for practice-based learning.

Average turnaround time is 12 weeks, with an average of 3-4 weeks to allocate and review new contracts. This approach keeps volume manageable, although expectations regarding timelines can be more challenging; where delays do occur, these are often beyond the control of the contracts team.

Areas for further development and improvement include updating the request forms, improving communications, including by further developing relationships with hubs and PIs, developing accessible progress reports, providing clear guidance documents and through workshops.

Sheffield's Five Core model for allocating contracts

2.5 Managing volume, complexity, and risk

Introduction

This section explores the perceived complexity of various contract types and changes over the past five years. Notable increases in complexity are identified in export licence applications, data agreements, and multilateral collaboration agreements. Larger institutions demonstrate lower average costs and processing times per contract. Sign-off routes predominantly involve line manager approval, and the use of e-signature software has increased since 2018. Instances of contractual disputes resulting in arbitration or litigation are rare, but inherent risks remain.

Changes in complexity and number of contract types

Respondents were asked to report the perceived complexity of different contract types and how they feel this has changed over the last five years (Figure 16).

Across respondents as a whole, significant increases in complexity are noted in relation to export licence applications, data agreements and multilateral collaboration agreements. There are a range of reasons for this, including COVID, Brexit, legislative changes (data protection, export control, National Security and Investment Act) (in the UK), an increased focus on foreign interference or indigenous knowledge (in Australia), and wider use of collaborations.

Figure 16 Level of contract complexity and change over recent years

A broad categorisation of contract types by complexity suggests that “more complex” contracts form the largest area of contract teams work

Using the levels of complexity assigned to each contract type in Figure 16, a broad categorisation was made of contracts as confidentiality agreements (“least complex”), amendments, “less complex” (clinical site agreements and everything to the left of it), or “more complex” (everything to the right of clinical site agreements).

Using this categorisation, it would appear that “more complex” contract types form the largest area of contract teams’ work in 2022(/23) (Figure 17).

Figure 17 Categorisation of contract types by level of complexity

UK universities are more likely to stipulate the jurisdiction of the defending party

Contracts are interpreted in different ways depending on the choice of governing law. University will prefer for their contracts to be governed by the law of their own country, not least because they will understand these laws better than laws of other countries. This is not always possible where parties to a contract are constituted in different countries.

When dealing with foreign partners, stipulating a mutually agreeable neutral jurisdiction is the most common approach to governing law among UK participants, whilst Australian participants are more likely to remain silent on governing law and jurisdiction.

Sign-off authority most often lies with a line manager

Amongst both UK and Australian respondents, sign-off by a line manager (e.g. Director of Research Office, Director of Legal Services) or their delegate is the most frequently used sign-off route (13 out of 24) (Figure 18), generally accompanied by a formal briefing document (Figure 19).

Related to this, in 2018 we noted very little use of e-signature software for contract sign off, noting that participants reported that securing wet ink signatures was an onerous task. This is a marked difference in 2023 responses, discussed further in '2.6 Systems and reporting'.

Figure 18
Sign-off authority

Figure 19
Further information provided to the signatory

Use of template agreements

Institutions were asked about the sector standard contract templates that they issue and accept and the nature of changes they may make to these templates (Figure 20).

In the UK, updated Brunswick, original Brunswick agreements, Lambert templates and Health Research Authority templates are most frequently issued as is or in amended form. In Australia, ARC and NHMRC multi-institutional agreements are most frequently issued as is.

It was also noted that Australian universities undertaking medical research are obliged to use the Medicines Australia contract templates. In the UK, use of the Brunswick and

Lambert template agreements is voluntary, use of the HRA templates is strongly preferred for NHS bodies, and use of the Information Commissioner’s Office IDTA is mandatory (but for very limited circumstances).

Figure 20 Issuing and acceptance of templates used in UK and Australian institutions.

Acceptance of contracts using templates	Accept as is		ICO International data transfer Original Brunswick	ICO International data transfer Lambert Original Brunswick Updated Brunswick	Health Research Authority x7 ICO International data transfer x4 Lambert Original Brunswick x3 Updated Brunswick x5 ARC Multi-institutional x3 NHMRC Multi-institutional x3
	Accept with minor amendments	Health Research Authority Lambert Original Brunswick x4 Updated Brunswick x4	ICO International data transfer Lambert x6 Original Brunswick x3 Updated Brunswick	Health Research Authority x3 ICO International data transfer x4 Lambert x7 Original Brunswick x5 Updated Brunswick x7	Health Research Authority ICO International data transfer Lambert x2 Original Brunswick x2 Updated Brunswick ARC Multi-institutional NHMRC Multi-institutional
	Not sure/not applicable	Health Research Authority x7 ICO International data transfer x6 Lambert ARC Multi-institutional NHMRC Multi-institutional			
		Not used	Used as a reference point only	Issued in amended form	Issued as is
Use of templates when issuing contracts					

Only a minority of respondents report any amount of arbitration / litigation in the last five years

We asked respondents for instances of contractual disputes resulting in arbitration or litigation to understand the profile of serious disputes arising under research contracts. We did not ask for quantitative data for informal disputes that are resolved prior to arbitration or litigation as there is no clear definition of an informal dispute. Narrative responses noted that disputes were most often resolved informally and may include, for example, internal agreement to write off debt

Most respondents from both the UK and Australia (18 out of 24) report no external arbitration or litigation over the last 5 years (Figure 21). Amongst the minority of respondents (six out of 24) which do report such action, all report only one or two such instances. In the context of an overall volume of 93,549 new contracts administered in the UK in the five years covered by this survey, this suggests a maximum of 10 contracts are reported to have led to formal arbitration or litigation (0.01%). However, other institutions refer to some disputes relating to contracts which have occurred, but which have not been formally escalated by external routes. The picture is slightly different in the smaller sample of Australian universities, where one or two contracts have led to a formal external process. This is in the context of a total volume of 10,523 new contracts in the survey period (in comparison to which two contracts would be 0.02%).

In January 2024, a high-profile legal case involving a research contract was reported. A commercial company claimed more than £100 million (A\$180m) from a UK University (which was not a participant in this benchmarking exercise) for breach of contract. The High Court found the University liable for £1 million (A\$1.8m). While litigation is rare in research contracts, this case demonstrates there are risks inherent in research contracts that require careful and deliberate management.

Figure 21
Reported levels of litigation and arbitration

Bilateral research contracts and services rendered were the contract types most frequently subject to litigation

Where formal arbitration or litigation has occurred, these most frequently relate to research contracts (bilateral) (4) or services rendered (by the University) (3).

It is noted that institutions which have reported external litigation or arbitration may report multiple contract types as having been the subject of such action (Figure 22).

Figure 22
Agreement types subject to external litigation

CASE STUDY: Managing volume, complexity and risk using standard terms and conditions for the knowledge exchange office

Edge Hill University (UK)

Edge Hill recently invested in a new Knowledge Exchange Office, creating four new roles. The KE office wants to operate quickly and at scale. It is separate from the Research Office, which is where the in-house contracts team is located.

To facilitate efficient management of a potentially large volume of KEO contracts, particularly for quick and uncomplicated agreements, standard terms and conditions were developed, based on a combination of previous work and previous terms and conditions. If a funder or client rejects the terms and wishes to negotiate a different agreement, or if the agreement is more complex, it is referred to the RO contracts team for review and to be progressed separately.

2.6 Systems and reporting

Introduction

This section explores developments in technology adoption and reporting practices within contracts functions. In 2018, dedicated systems were scarce, but by 2023, 80% of participants report systemic or operational use of e-signature software, a significant shift catalysed by the COVID-19 pandemic. The survey also reveals improved reporting of 13 key metrics, with most metrics reported by over 40% of participants. Adoption of research Information management systems and contract management software has risen, but barriers such as budget constraints and limited team capacity persist.

Between 2018 and 2023, we see notable progress in the use and availability of supporting systems for research contract management

In 2018, we reported that dedicated systems to effectively support research contracts management were largely absent in the UK. At that time some Australian participants reported the use of dedicated research contracts modules within a commercial research information management systems. Consequently, contracts functions had difficulties in reporting metrics that related to workflows, performance and productivity of the function. In addition, despite e-signature solutions being widely available, systematised use of e-signature software was absent in 2018.

In 2023 we anticipated seeing considerable progress in these areas and we expanded the questions around the use of systems and technologies, in part to reflect the emergence of AI-based assistive technologies.

From low use in 2018, the practice of using e-signature software is well-established in 2023

80% of the 24 participants report systemic or operational use of e-signature software. This is a marked development since 2018, when none of the 30 participants reported using it operationally. In practice, the COVID-19 pandemic and enforced remote working practices catalysed the changes within institutions to enable adoption of this established technology.

The availability and use of metrics for management of contract functions has improved since 2018

The survey inquired about the availability and utilization of 13 metrics crucial for research contract management performance and reporting. In 2018, only total contract throughput was regularly or ad-hoc reported by over 50% of participants, whereas in 2023 significant improvement is evident, with most metrics reported by at least 40% of participants.

Metrics that are not available to more than 40% of the participating contracts functions include:

- contract turnaround time by contracts officer;
- contract turnaround time by owner; and
- contracts with disputes arising.

Those most frequently available and regularly reported are contract throughput (total), whilst those most frequently reported on an ad hoc basis are slow-moving contracts (Figure 23). We did not ask institutions to report the actual metrics as institutions use different methodologies for each metric which makes a comparison of equivalent measures impossible.

Figure 23

Use and availability of metrics / reports on contracts activity

CASE STUDY: Using data for contracting insights and uplift

The Research Contracts team at RMIT University uses data and metrics to manage its workflows and allocate resourcing, and to provide the research community with visibility over status and progress of contracts.

RMIT University (Australia)

The data tells stakeholders, researchers and the team where trends or “pain points” are, which then informs what is required to achieve successful outcomes and improve efficiencies, whether this is engagement with partners, additional resources, or training or professional development.

The team currently uses a contracts module in its research management system as its primary data capture mechanism, complemented with dashboard-style reporting using PowerBI. In 2024, the team will transition to a new system, presenting greater opportunities for:

- generating more relevant insights;
- reduction in duplication of data entry;
- improved transparency;
- more nuanced ability to demonstrate the team’s value; and
- cross-team collaboration, enabled by a better view of the “pipeline”.

RMIT’s experience with data collection, management and reporting has highlighted the importance of ensuring that only the most relevant and useful data is captured, and that it’s captured at the right point of a project’s lifecycle. This ensures data sets are manageable but still provide valuable insights for teams and leaders across the University.

Systems have changed since 2018, with growing implementation of formal software solutions to manage contracts

Since 2018, adoption of Research Information Management Systems (RIMS), Current Research Information Systems (CRIS) and contract management software has increased, with 15 out of 24 institutions reporting implementation of these (Figure 24). Institutions with a lower research income (less than £10m (A\$18m)) are less likely to have any dedicated software.

Figure 24
Software description

Awareness of newer innovations is high but operational uptake remains limited

19 institutions have either systemic or operational use of e-signature software, 14 use structured contract request workflows and 12 report some level of use of visualisation tools for management information. Most institutions are at least aware of newer innovations, including AI review of third-party contracts (12 plus 1 operational user), automated or AI-assisted drafting of new agreements (13 plus 1 active user) and Word add-ins for contract drafting and review (14 aware, no use reported) (Figure 25). Use of structured contract request workflows appears to be more established in the UK than in Australia.

Lack of budget, lack of contracts team capacity to investigate potential solutions and lack of wider institutional capacity to implement software are seen as the most significant barriers to adoption of contracts management software.

Figure 25 The use and awareness of software solutions for contracts management (UK and Australia)

CASE STUDY:
Implementing Worktribe and its effect on ways of working

University of Leicester (UK)

Prior to the implementation of Worktribe, contracts were managed and stored in a range of different systems, including on a shared drive, in the financial management system and in a CRM database. Worktribe helps to provide a clearer journey for the PI, from initiation to completion, whilst providing consistent document storage, visibility controls and a store for negotiation notes. It also helps to add clarity, such as regarding the point at which due diligence should be undertaken on partners, and when governance or other University services should be involved in reviewing agreements.

The Worktribe dashboard provides summary information about individual agreements, their contract type, status and priority level, whilst data reporting, using Worktribe data via an external system, is able to summarise working days spent on agreements, at College, School, contract type level and can be used for workload management.

The overall impact of Worktribe Contracts has been to improve the transparency of the contracts process for academics, to improve reporting (including through interoperable data which can be analysed in PowerBI) and to lay the groundwork for a further piece of work relating to academic engagement.

3. Future considerations

The benchmarking exercises identifies areas for future consideration or action

This report has highlighted a number of areas where further actions or work may be warranted. These are summarised here:

- Addressing a challenging recruitment and retention landscape, noting how easily skills relating to contract roles can be transferred to other sectors (public and private), often in roles offering better pay and terms and conditions. Capacity and resilience can be improved by a pipeline of training roles, such as degree apprenticeships.
- Building on opportunities to enhance the provision of training (including on a collaborative regional or partnership basis).
- Sharing of insight and experience of adoption of dedicated software for research contract management, informing procurement decisions and optimising use of data for metrics and management through visualisation and enhanced business intelligence.
- Scoping and awareness-raising regarding the practical use and benefits of technologies (including AI) which can assist in contracts work, together with a shared commitment to work with these as normal practice.
- Working across the sector to consider areas where further standardisation may be helpful. For example, exploring harmonisation of data and measures to enable comparisons to be made between institutions on key metrics.

Addressing the challenge of improving recruitment and retention

The perception of both retention and recruitment becoming harder within research contracts management suggests challenges for the future development and health of this area of professional specialisation. Enhanced networking opportunities and training offers (including on a local, regional and partnership basis) may help to address these issues. Creation of a greater number of attractive junior posts with clear training and progression pathways, including apprenticeships (whether on a legal or research office pathway), may address these challenges.

The recruitment landscape for contracts officers is distinctive (compared to other roles within a typical research office) as directly comparable roles are available across a wide range of public and private sector organisations. This creates a competitive recruitment market and means university-based contracts functions may need to work harder to recruit, retain and develop qualified and experienced staff.

Wider adoption of dedicated software for research contract management has been seen, but gaps remain

We note the increasing use of systems dedicated to the needs of research contract functions in the UK. However, smaller, less research-intensive universities may find challenges in resourcing such systems, creating potential gaps within the sector.

For teams with existing systems, there is a trend towards greater integration between systems and in particular business intelligence tools, which enable better availability and visualisation of responsive management information relating to contract management. Within the sector, increased sharing of approaches to this area may be of benefit, building on evidence available about commonly-used systems.

Hybrid working is here to stay

Although there is relatively low adoption of entirely remote working within contracts functions, it is clear that some amount of hybrid working has now become embedded within institutional working practices and is likely to remain so, particularly given its reported position as a tool to support recruitment and retention. Given the challenges of recruitment noted above, some institutions may consider permitting staff to work fully remotely to tap into a broader recruitment market, although others see significant pitfalls with this approach.

Managing risk in relation to contracts activity

As in 2018, due diligence and risk management were a recurring theme in the study. Since 2018, institutions have developed processes and ownership for due diligence; however, work remains to ensure the results of due diligence are connected to contractual considerations.

The responses to the question about external arbitration and litigation reveal a very low number of contracts needing resolution through this level of formal external process. That should give confidence to contract teams that their role in getting contracting arrangements right is generally successful.

It is also worth noting that the COVID-19 pandemic represented an unprecedented and unpredicted disruptive event. In response, contracts functions appear to have been largely resilient, with some process efficiencies – such as widespread adoption of e-signatures – catalysed by necessity.

Anticipating the technological shifts of the next five years

The adoption of e-signatures has advanced significantly over the last five years, but undoubtably contracts functions in universities were late to adopt this ‘standard’ business practice software. As yet there are no signs of a similar step change in adoption of other innovative tools such as AI for reviewing or drafting contracts. While there are clear barriers to contracts functions adopting standalone AI platforms, as AI becomes integrated into existing tools (such as Microsoft’s Copilot within the Office 365 suite), we expect to see greater use of assistive technologies. Challenges and costs of surveying the market to source appropriate solutions might be solved through sector bodies. Good dissemination and sharing of the practical use and benefits of using such technologies will be key to wider adoption.

Responding to legislative changes

In an uncertain global and political climate, the pace of legislative change and the impact on this on contracts functions may continue to grow. In the UK, GDPR and the Data Protection Act 2018 appears to have led to increased volumes of data agreements, and the Trusted Research agenda including the National Security and Investment Act 2021 has introduced additional legislative burden. In Australia, similar changes have been seen in relation to foreign influence and interference and to agreements with indigenous peoples. There may also be lessons for Australia in the UK institutions’ experience of the growth of data agreements since 2018, especially if Australian data protection or privacy laws were to be reviewed over coming years.

Standardisation within the university research sector

A significant volume of research contracts are dealing with “in country, university-to-university” collaborations. Identifying ways to minimise the cost and time of such negotiations and to further increase use of templates that require little or no bespokeing

(and adopting consistent conventions and techniques, such as use of redlining) is likely to have benefits for the sector as a whole.

Participants in this project expressed interest in comparing metrics across institutions; exploring potential harmonisation of data and measures may be another area where further standardisation would be helpful. This accords with recommendations from the UK Government-commissioned [Tickell review of Research Bureaucracy](#) and ongoing work with the UK's Department for Science, Innovation and Technology (DSIT) and the sector to improve standardisation.

How to define "quality" for research contract management?

A continuing challenge highlighted in the 2018 exercise is the difficulty of assessing and defining quality in relation to research contract management. Metrics which measure volumes, throughput and time are only meaningful if agreements are delivered to the right quality standard. Defining quality in relation to the modern research contracts function is not straightforward, and needs to take into account a variety of factors – stakeholder perceptions, risk, speed, the negotiating "red lines" and compliance with sponsor obligations. We do not yet see evidence of a trend towards clearer articulation of institutional approaches to quality and / or negotiation parameters within research contracts functions in institutions. However, establishing these parameters is a precondition for successful adoption of AI tools and the realisation of efficiency savings. As such, this is an area where we expect to see further developments over the coming years.

Glossary

A glossary of the terms and agreement types used in the report and charts.

Contract volume Participants reported the number of contracts (agreements) completed in each year examined by the study. This is not the same as the number of “projects” as some projects may have more than one agreement.

FTE Full time equivalent staff

HEI Higher Education Institution

Legal Services The term legal services is used within the report as a generic description of this common university function. Typically these are central functions providing a wide range of legal advice on issues relating to HR, students, commercial and business matters, and this can include research contract responsibilities.

Research income Participants reported the total research grants and contracts income of the university, including income not supported by the research contracts function. The research grants and contracts income is the income meeting the funding income categories for HESA (UK) and HERDC (Australia).

Research Office The term research office is used within the report as a generic description of this common university function. A research office will typically have responsibility for pre and post award management and approval of funding applications. It may also be responsible for research contracts, consultancy and other services rendered income activities, partnerships with industry, technology transfer, research business development, impact and research policy.

Agreement and Contract types The survey sought information on a range of agreement/contract types. A number of these are referenced in the report. The types, definitions and associated acronyms are listed below.

Clinical Site Agreements Agreements for specific sites within a clinical trial. These specify at the site level the roles and responsibilities of the Chief investigator, particularly if they are delegated sponsor tasks.

Clinical Trial Agreements Agreements related to the conduct and management of a clinical trial, including the relevant standards applicable to the trial (e.g. for Clinical Trials of Investigational Medicinal Product (CTIMPs) this would include the Clinical Trials Regulations).

Collaboration Agreements (multilateral) Agreements detailing the arrangements for multiparty collaborations, which may include a range of university, industry, public and end user organisations. Some may be entirely comprised of university partners.

Consultancy Agreements	Agreements related to the delivery of consultancy services, typically research-related and part of a university's commercial offer.
Data Agreements	Agreements relating to the sharing of data. In the UK, this has a specific meaning relating to data sharing agreements to show compliance and accountability for the purposes of UK GDPR.
European Commission Agreements	UK only. Agreements relating to collaborations funded through the EU R&D programmes, typically via Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe, and involving universities, business and other research users.
Export licence applications	Export licences form part of a Government's strategic export controls. In the UK, this covers export or trade in goods, software or technology (including data, information and technical assistance) which might be subject to export controls.
Fellowship Agreements	Agreements relating to the award and funding of fellowships.
Foreign influence / interference Agreements	Australia only. Agreements which are related to Australian law governing foreign interference, which is defined as an activity carried out by, or on behalf of, a foreign power, which is coercive, corrupting, deceptive or clandestine, and contrary to Australia's sovereignty, values and national interests.
Framework Agreements	An agreement between one or more contracting authorities and one or more economic operators, the purpose of which is to establish the terms governing contracts to be awarded during a given period, in particular with regard to price and, where appropriate, the quantity envisaged.
International Research Project Agreements	Agreements relating to research projects with an international partnership dimension, typically where sponsoring organisations are based overseas, or a project has collaborating partners in overseas territories. Legal jurisdictions and enhanced risks are additional elements to consider in these cases.
KTP Agreements	UK only. Agreements relating to the national "Knowledge Transfer Partnership" scheme, typically bilateral agreements between the university and co-funding company, but recognising the terms of the grant offer letter from the sponsor (Innovate UK).
Licence Agreements (software or non-software)	Agreements relating to the exploitation of IP arising from university research, the agreement allows the university to grant a licence to the external organisation, typically a business. The licence is a consent by the owner to the use of IP in exchange for money or something else of value. ²

² The 2015 WIPO "Successful Technology Licensing" guide is a useful resource.

Material Transfer Agreements	A contract that governs the transfer of tangible research materials between two organisations, when the recipient intends to use it for his or her own research purposes. The MTA defines the rights of the provider and the recipient with respect to the materials and any derivatives.
Memoranda of Understanding	MoUs are a type of agreement typically between two parties. They express a convergence of will between the parties, indicating an intended common line of action. It is often used in cases where parties either do not imply a legal commitment or in situations where the parties cannot create a legally enforceable agreement. They are common in international partnerships, particularly in relation to China.
Research Contracts (bilateral)	Bilateral research contracts relating to the funding of specific projects.
Research Subcontracts	Agreements relating to the delivery of elements (e.g. analytical, specific work packages) of university research by third parties.
Services Rendered Agreements	Agreements relating to non-research services provided by the university to external organisations. These may relate to a variety of activities, for example routine testing or analysis or the use of facilities or equipment.
Services Agreements	Agreements relating to services required from 3 rd parties and delivered to the university (distinct from <i>research subcontracts</i>).
Spinout company agreements	Agreements relating to the formation of a spin-out company, typically a number of agreements are required. They cover a range of issues, including: shareholding and ownership, the involvement of university staff in the spin-out, investment and funding into the company, the arrangements for the company accessing university facilities, IP licences and agreements around future IP (from university research).
Studentship Agreements	Agreements relating to the sponsorship of PhD studentships, typically by industry or other research users. Funding may be for the whole studentship or to co-fund part of the studentship costs.

Appendix A. The consulting team

Research Consulting

Rob Johnson (Managing Director) Rob works with universities, sector bodies and academic publishers in the UK and overseas to improve practice in research management and impact. Formerly Head of Research Operations at the University of Nottingham, Rob brings an in-depth knowledge of the research ecosystem within higher education. He has an in-depth understanding of university pre-award and contracts processes, and delivered the two previous contracts benchmarking studies in 2013 and 2018.

Dan King (Director) Dan is a research and knowledge exchange specialist with over 25 years' experience. Dan has held senior positions at the University of Nottingham (2001-17) and Nottingham Trent University (2017-18). He previously worked at EPSRC and in research development (University of Warwick). Dan has delivered benchmarking studies in association with ARMA and as part of the 2018 Research Contracts Benchmarking project.

Angharad Roberts (Senior Analyst) Angharad has over 20 years' experience in academic administration and librarianship including as a Research Strategy and Policy Manager and as Secretary of a University Research and Enterprise Committee, facilitating strategic decision-making relating to research and enterprise. Angharad has worked alongside research contracts teams in supporting institutional preparations for REF 2021 and compiling annual HE-BCI returns.

Frances Palmer (Associate Consultant) Frances has experience of research and data analysis, utilising both qualitative and quantitative research methods. Frances previously worked in the Enterprise team at Nottingham Trent University, working with SMEs and stakeholders to research and analyse the quality and impact of research, projects, and programmes, on businesses, the economy, and the community. She was responsible for the data for two annual HE-BCI reports.

Associate Consultants

Tom Morgan (Legal expert) Tom is a commercial lawyer at international law firm CMS working in the Technology, Media, Intellectual Property and Competition team. Tom worked at the University of Bristol for over 11 years, working up from a Contracts Officer to the Head of Research Contracts and Research Compliance. Tom provides expert, specialist advice on high-risk research and commercial matters in a complex legal and regulatory landscape.

Mark Hochman (Australia expert) Mark, based in Tasmania, Australia, has 20 years of experience as a senior manager in an office offering a one stop shop to research administration. He is now self-employed as a director of Research Management Resources. He was the president of the Australasian Research Management Society 2007/2008.

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